

DEVELOPING NATIONAL IDENTITY THROUGH NATIONAL GAMES: ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE KYRGYZ GAME “ORDO”

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Abstract. *This study examines the Kyrgyz national game “ordo” and its role in shaping national identity. Ordo originates from the idea of “taking the Khan’s horde” and reflects military-strategic logic. Field observations show that the game fosters collective discipline, strategic thinking, and perseverance among players. The data of field observations conducted at permanent playgrounds for the game “ordo” near the main building of the Kyrgyz National University named after Zhusup Balasagyn served as materials for the research. Data collection included external and in-depth observation, interviews with participants, as well as photo and video recording. These materials allowed tracing the social functions of the game, its organization and influence on the formation of collective behavior and national identity. Moreover, a comparative analysis was conducted between the Kyrgyz game “ordo” and the Kazakh game “asyk atu”, which allowed revealing their features, social functions and influencing the formation of national identity. The results of the study represent that “ordo” contributes to establishing tradition as a “living experience” in the urban-educational space, strengthening offline socialization of young people, reinforcing intergenerational continuity and etiquette norms (respect for elders and respect for the younger ones) through experience, and developing team spirit and strategic thinking.*

Key words: *Ordo, asyk games, national identity, spiritual culture, urban space, university, generational continuity, ethnosport*

Introduction

In the context of globalization and the rapid development of digital communication, the social functions of traditional cultural practices are being reconfigured, and a number of phenomena are moving from the level of “heritage”, “historical memory” to the level of “everyday experience” and “living culture”. In this process, the social role of folk creativity (games, rituals, artistic activities, oral culture, customs and traditions) becomes an effective channel for the renewal and strengthening of national identity. Within the framework of the research project, folk knowledge and folk experience are considered as mechanisms for the differentiation and revitalization of spiritual culture.

In the context of globalization, the issue of preserving and developing national culture and national identity has become one of the most important scientific and social issues for many countries. National identity is an important social phenomenon that unites the historical memory, cultural values, traditions and customs of the people. K.M. Turgumbaeva in her article “National Identity in the Conditions of Globalization” considered national identity as a means of forming national identity in the context of globalization [1]. Fadhel et al. claimed that national identity is a complex concept that reflects a nation's characteristics, including language, customs, arts, culture, history, and beliefs. It plays a crucial role in fostering national pride and unity, distinguishing one nation from another in the international arena [2]. National identity is important and it is a reflection of a nation's condition and a distinguishing factor from other nations. It emphasizes the need for conscious efforts, such as civic education, to strengthen national code of each nationality [3].

In this regard, national games strengthen national identity by fostering a shared sense of community through regional coordination, socio-cultural synergy, and economic collaboration,

enhancing group interactions, and promoting the concept of “shared destiny, shared honor, shared survival, and shared future” through sports [4]. Asiimwe A. mentioned that national games strengthen national identity by creating shared cultural experiences and fostering communal ties. They serve as platforms for nations to express pride and showcase strengths, reinforcing political narratives and enhancing social cohesion, while also highlighting societal divisions [5].

They are considered as one of the most effective means of preserving the cultural heritage of the people and passing it on to the younger generation. National games perform not only an entertainment function, but also carry out educational, social and cultural functions. They are a traditional phenomenon that is an important component of the cultural heritage of a people. They reflect the historical experience, lifestyle, worldview, customs and values of a particular people. National games, as one of the cultural traditions that have been formed over the centuries and passed down from generation to generation, occupy a special place in the spiritual life of society. Therefore, national games are considered not only a means of entertainment, but also a phenomenon that has educational, social and cultural significance.

In addition, national games foster teamwork, cooperation, courage, agility, and responsibility. These qualities strengthen social ties in society and help maintain the unity of the national community. Baimuratov, K., & Nurmatov, Kh. V. Explored the benefits of national games and identified that national games develop qualities such as courage, friendship, unity of action, mutual assistance, and understanding, alongside physical attributes like agility, strength, and endurance, fostering teamwork and cooperation among primary school students [6]. The shared experience and cultural symbols formed through national games contribute to the preservation of the cultural integrity of the people and the development of national consciousness.

In the context of modern globalization, the issue of preserving and developing national culture is of particular importance. From this point of view, the study of national games and their use in the process of education and upbringing is one of the effective means of strengthening national identity. Therefore, it is relevant to consider the role of traditional national games in the formation of national culture and national identity from a scientific perspective.

Another important reason for studying this topic is to determine the role of national games in the formation of national consciousness of young people. In modern society, increasing the interest of young people in national culture and educating them to respect national values is one of the important tasks. Traditional games are considered one of the effective cultural and pedagogical tools for achieving this goal.

This article examines the historical formation, social and cultural function of the national game of the Kyrgyz people “Ordo” asyk, as well as its role in the formation and development of national identity. In addition, the impact of the traditional game on the recognition of national values by young people, the preservation of cultural heritage and the strengthening of national consciousness is analyzed.

In international ethnosports descriptions, the concept of “ordo” is interpreted as “khan's horde/palace, headquarters”, and it is indicated that the game reflects the model of “battle to capture the khan's horde” This semantic layer allows us to analyze the social semantics of “ordo”, not limited to marksmanship, but in connection with the concepts of collective order, strategy and symbolic power.

Different studies have been devoted to “ordo” and its importance. Baimuratov and Nurmatov investigated this game and concluded that “Ordo” is a Kyrgyz national game that emphasizes teamwork and strategy. It develops physical qualities such as strength, agility, and coordination, while also fostering values like friendship and mutual assistance among participants, making it beneficial for primary school students [6].

The Kyrgyz national game “Ordo” is a traditional game that emphasizes teamwork and strategy. It is played by various age groups and serves educational purposes, fostering skills such as cooperation and understanding of rules among participants [7]. Ordo is a traditional Kyrgyz game that holds significant cultural importance, embodying social values, fairness, and strategic thinking.

The game is integral to Kyrgyz heritage, promoting national identity and fostering ethnocultural competence among learners through its historical and educational aspects [8].

These studies emphasize the cultural, educational and educational significance of the national game ordo. It is noted in the works that ordo is a traditional Kyrgyz game that develops physical qualities such as strength, agility and coordination, and also forms the skills of teamwork, strategic thinking and mutual assistance among participants. The researchers also emphasize that the game is used in the educational process and promotes learning the rules of interaction, the development of cooperation and respect for others. In addition, the Horde is considered an important element of the cultural heritage of the Kyrgyz people, which transmits social values, contributes to the formation of ethno-cultural competence and strengthens national identity.

This article considers how the national game of “ordo” is practiced at the present time and what significance it has in the development of national identity. The study analyzes the current state of the game, the forms of its preservation and popularization, as well as its role in the transfer of cultural values, traditions and historical memory to the younger generation. Particular attention is paid to the fact that participation in the game of ordo contributes to the strengthening of the feeling of belonging to one's people, the formation of respect for national heritage and the development of national identity. Moreover, a comparative analysis of the Kyrgyz game “ordo” and the Kazakh national game “asyk atu” is carried out, which allows us to consider their role in the preservation of cultural traditions and the development of national identity among different Turkic peoples.

Materials and methods

The data of field observations conducted on Ordo Square near the main building of the Kyrgyz National University named after Zhusup Balasagyn were used as research material. The material was collected on the basis of external observation, in-depth observation and interviews with participants, as well as by means of photo and video recording.

Results and discussions

The game of “ordo” originated from the idea of “taking the khan's horde” and is associated with the logic of military-strategic training. This symbolic structure was also indirectly reflected in field observations: in the communication of the players, such semantic orientations as “horde”, “center”, “tactics” prevailed. Ordo was thus observed at the social level as an experience that formed such behavioral patterns as:

- *obedience to the collective goal* (agreement within the team, order of turns);
- *strategic calculation* (tactics of entering the field, preliminary assessment of the outcome of the blow);
- *willpower and endurance* (striving for a second blow, maintaining the order of the game after an unsuccessful blow).

Also of particular importance in the field data is the presence of two grounds for the “ordo” game in the complex of the Zhusup Balasagyn Kyrgyz National University. Its location in the city space, in the university complex, and the training of the national team there indicate that “ordo” has moved beyond the ethnographic-festive context and has become an everyday urban experience. That is, along with the participants of the national team, young people, university students, and transient city residents can actively participate in the game [9]. The presence of a permanent playground in an educational environment where young people are concentrated - firstly, makes the national experience not a “random/festive spectacle”, but an accessible everyday activity; secondly, it reduces online isolation in the digital age and strengthens offline social ties; thirdly, it encourages young people who are superficial/indifferent to tradition to unite in one environment through play (softly conveying complex cultural meaning through the form of a simple “game”).

Figure - 1, 2. Photos taken during the training of the national team of the “ordo” game
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This conclusion indicates the consolidation of national identity “through institutional space”: the university is not only a place of education, but also a social platform for the production of cultural experience.

During the field study, it was recorded that the “ordo” game is played by “hard-bodied” young people over 14 years old and adults, the field has a diameter of 14 m, up to 7 people participate at a time, the field is marked with two circles - outer/inner, and asyk/abalak is thrown from outside the circle.

And the official description of the V World Nomad Games held in Astana Kazakhstan [10], states that Ordo is held among men, its participants are over 18 years old, and the diameter of the circle of the field is 12 m. Therefore, the tradition can adapt to the “local environment” and maintain variable standards. This variability is not interpreted as a “weakness of tradition”, but rather as its vitality and flexibility: on the one hand, the official competition regulations, and on the other hand, the everyday practice of the community.

The constant elements of the “ordo” game are clearly described in open sources. For example, it is indicated that the player's entry into the circle is associated with tactical conditions such as the abalak (central part) should be no more than 40 cm from the nearest “asyk”, and no more than 20 cm from the “khan”. This determines the synthesis of ordo “shooting + strategy”. From field research, it was noted that the asyk distance is determined by one step or half a step (foot) and the traditional measurements of the arm, elbow (hand).

The most important result of the conducted field case is the play of young people together with adults. Playing on the same field, from a teenage boy to a physically strong adult man, socially implements generational continuity through joint action, serves as a “public school” of informal education. In this regard, the function of “ordo”, close to a social institution, is evident: it is not just a game, but an experience that regulates and conveys the codes of social relations of the nation. Thus, through one national game, we can see the depth of national knowledge. Games related to “asyk” are widespread in the culture of Turkic-speaking peoples. The Kazakh people also consider “asyk atu”, “khan talapai” as national games, explaining the connection of many children's games with asyk with the basis of nomadic economic and cultural life. However, today these games remain as children's games in rural areas and before adolescence. In recent years, due to the celebration of Nauryz at the national level and the redefinition of the content of this holiday, we observe that asyk games are held as a festive event, but it has not yet become an everyday cultural experience among adolescents and young people. However, in the current sports format, “asyk atu” is included in the competitive game. The list of the V World Nomad Games [11] includes the team composition of the national game “asyk atu” (men / women, coaches, representative, referee and participants over 18 years old). Table 1 compares these two national games.

Table 1 Comparison of two national games

Criteria	Ordo (Kyrgyz national game)	Asyk atu (Kazakh national game)
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Symbolic meaning	It symbolizes the “capture of the Khan's palace”, reflects historical and cultural ideas.	It is connected with the tradition of shooting and competitive shooting
Participants	Young people and adults	Children and teenagers play traditionally
Character of the game	Team game with a clearly expressed strategy	Individual game on the mark (in modern practice possible team formats)
Game strategy	Complex tactics of "entering the space" and collective interaction	Main focus on accuracy and individual skill
Modern status	Preserves the traditional format and cultural-symbolic meaning	Currently it is institutionalized and developing as a kind of sport
Role in the formation of identity	Activates collective discipline, strategic thinking and historical-symbolic imagination	Contributes to the preservation of traditional games and the development of sports skills

The Kyrgyz game “ordo” symbolizes the “capture of the horde” and reflects historical and cultural ideas. It is played by young people and adults, and it is a team game with a clearly expressed strategy and tactics of “entering the space”. The game develops collective discipline, strategic thinking and historical-symbolic imagination. Unlike “ordo”, the Kazakh game of “asyk atu” is traditionally associated with children and teenagers, is focused on accuracy and individual mastery, and is now institutionalized as a kind of sport. Thus, “ordo” activates to collective discipline, strategic thinking and historical-symbolic imagination, and “asyk atu” preserves traditions and develops sports skills.

Both games play an important role in the formation of national identity. Through the team game, strategic thinking and symbolic reflection of the historical and cultural heritage, “orda” contributes to the development of collective discipline and a sense of belonging to the people. “asyk atu”, preserves traditional skills passing on cultural customs to children and adolescents, maintains a connection with national history and culture. Both games, despite the differences in format and participants, allow the young generation to connect with traditions, learn the values of their people and strengthen ethno-cultural self-awareness. Thus, they simultaneously perform an educational, educational and cultural-symbolic function in society.

Conclusion

The results of the field study show that the national Kyrgyz game “ordo” serves as a social mechanism for strengthening national identity in the context of globalization and the digital era. The constant presence of ordo squares in university spaces indicates that the tradition has entered everyday life and, by strengthening the offline socialization of young people, consolidates national memory and living culture at the practical level. The command-strategic nature of “ordo”, the symbolism of the “khan's horde” and the mixed intergenerational game format elevate it not only to entertainment, but also to the level of cultural and social regulatory practice, cultural memory of historical consciousness. The differences between field practice and official regulations (age limit, square size) are interpreted as an important indicator of the ability of the tradition to adapt to the environment.

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